

WAYS TO SOLUTION PROBLEMS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTROL OF PREPARATION OF YOUNG ATHLETES

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Annotation: The article presents the concept and ways to solve problems, as well as the structure of complex psychological control in the system of training sports reserves. Using the example of children and adolescents, the expediency of including neuropsychological and intellectual signs of special abilities in the control was experimentally substantiated.

Key words: psychological control, pentabasis principle, children, adolescents.

Introduction. In domestic sports, until recently, there has been no clear understanding of the psychological type of control over the development and formation of special abilities in the children's and youth age range [5]. This leads to a loss of information about the current state of special abilities and a limited possibility of predicting their genesis in combination with pedagogical control data. The consequence is errors in sports selection and poor individualization of training for both young and adult athletes [1, 3]. Confirmation of this at the state level can be the fact that their leadership, as a rule, remembers the need for psychological control in the system of training national teams six months before the next Olympics.

The problem of correlating psychological and pedagogical quality criteria and the actual assessment of special abilities is not sufficiently methodologically developed due to contradictions in the understanding of their structure. In one case, the system-forming feature is self-control and self-management of motor actions,

where the main role belongs to mental functions [2, 4, 6]. In another case, it is a functional (psychophysiological) component. The common point of agreement between different authors is the hierarchical understanding of the structure of special abilities. Each of the components corresponds to the work of fundamentally different systems of the human body – morphological, psychophysiological, sensory-cognitive, personal and motor [8, 9, 11].

However, the question of studying such regulatory systems as neuropsychic and intellectual, which underlie coordination ability, and their relationship with other motor and psychomotor abilities during the period of ascending ontogenesis, remains open to this day [10].

It is also well known that in training an athlete reinforces the stereotype of motor activity with a low level of mental stress, while in competition conditions this level can even exceed the maximum capabilities. Therefore, the relevance of the problem of psychological control is due to the increasing role of mental stress [7, 12, 13].

This type of control is of particular importance in the preparation of a sports reserve, since high psychophysical stress against the background of the active biosocial development of a teenager provokes the emergence of borderline states - neuroticism and psychopathization.

This problem also reflects the contradictions between the requirements of the tasks of psychological control of young athletes' preparedness and the possibilities of its implementation under a strict time limit, especially in competition conditions [14, 15]. We believe that its practical solution is appropriate based on the principle of simplicity and accessibility of the diagnostic procedure in the field. The same applies to techniques for self-regulation of mental readiness.

It is known that disorders of neuropsychic functions that ensure the preservation of motor analyzer zones limit the manifestation of coordination abilities, and, consequently, the achievement of high sports results. However, their criteria have not been used in sport psychology [16].

On the other hand, the contingent of young athletes is formed from schoolchildren who do not go in for sports, and the question naturally arises about the state of sensitivity, crisis and the contingency of the development of higher mental functions, physical and motor qualities in modern children and adolescents. Extensive research was carried out in the 1970-1980s against the background of acceleration. The last decade has seen a deceleration of development, and therefore a new data bank is needed.

In addition, the number of children and adolescents classified as at risk and with mental health problems who are no longer involved in sports is steadily growing every year. This indicates the need to search for factors that limit the psychophysical development of children and adolescents and means of developing the ability to self-manage brain activity.

From the standpoint of a systematic approach, the concept of psychological control of sports reserve training includes ideas about: the subject of control (psychogram of the sport and psychological passport of the athlete); object of control (types of mental readiness); control subsystems, or functions (psychological selection, forecast, monitoring, training), its components and structure. In the “object” we add an assessment of readiness for a specific training, in the “functions” we add forecast and training.

Level of general scientific categories — integration, active reflection, reactive reflection, reactive regulation, active regulation. The level of system categories, respectively, is neurodynamic unity, intellectual-reflexive proportionality, perceptual-psychomotor balance, affective-vegetative repeatability, energetic subordination. The level of psychological categories is conscious-subconscious, information-evaluative, correctional-executive, emotional, motivational-target. At this level, to the four components traditional for sports psychology, a fifth component is added - the conscious subconscious.

In psychodiagnostics, we consider it necessary to be guided by the following rules: an integrated approach to the selection of techniques and their

appropriateness to age, with a focus on the “zone of proximal development”; the use of motor and mental actions that do not require prior learning; the principle of the same external aspects of the diagnostic technique for any age and the clarity of the instructions the first time.

In addition, it is necessary to take into account that the most clearly critical “points” of ontogenesis appear in the development of the properties of the nervous system (the beginning and end of active puberty), as well as in the change of hereditary and environmental influences on intellectual functions (at 10–11 years and 14–15 years).

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Components of psychological control should include only the psychological component of special abilities, i.e. self-control and self-regulation: neuropsychic, perceptual intellectual, psychomotor, emotional-volitional, mental (ideomotor, symbolization) and specialized perceptions as the basis of coordination abilities.

As for the structure of control, that is, the method of internal interconnection of components, the analysis of the problem we are studying from the standpoint of a systems approach gave grounds for using the principle of pentabasis to combine general scientific, systemic and psychological categories. This principle turned out to be explicitly or implicitly laid in the basis of the theory and methodology of sports regarding models of control of voluntary movements, state of mental readiness, stress and psyche, personality, self-regulation of achievements, psychophysical rehabilitation, motivation for sports activity, reliability of activity,

personality activity, current segments of sports activity, types of psychological preparation and selection, psychomotor structure.

Taking into account the above, our proposed integrated structure of psychological control covers five levels of individuality and mental regulation of an athlete's activity.

Conclusions. Since neuropsychological and intellectual factors of development make different specific contributions to the genesis of motor abilities, starting from the early period of ontogenesis, depending on the age and gender of children and adolescents, this inevitably manifests itself in special abilities and should be taken into account when monitoring the readiness of young athletes.

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